

SPOUSAL COMMUNICATION, OPENNESS AND EXTRAVERSION AS PREDICTORS OF MARITAL INSTABILITY AMONG MARRIED TEACHERS IN SAGAMU LOCAL GOVERNMENT, OGUN STATE

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Abstract

Marital instability has been a huge problem in our society from the problem of divorce, single parenting, abusive relationships, rebellious children because of lack of proper training by both parents; these problems have fueled the passion to uncover the correlation of personality types and spousal communication as predictors to marital instability.

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The research instrument was validated and reliability test was done using Cronbach alpha analysis. The population is comprised of all married teachers in public schools in Sagamu local government in Ogun state. There are a total of 924 teachers in the 24 public schools, of which 108 out of the 924 teachers are either widowed, divorced, separated or single. A sample size of 300 was generated using Yamane Formulae.

The findings showed that personality types and spousal communication do not significantly contribute to marital instability in young couples in Ogun State. $(6,274)=30.950p<.005$). Also, there was no statistically significant contribution between openness and marital instability (Beta = .029, $t = .484$, $p >.05$) and extraversion (Beta = -.049, $t = -.1.024$, $p >.05$). Lastly, there was a significant contribution of spousal communication to marital instability among young couples in Ogun State. The result revealed significant results (Beta = -.608, $t = 12.796$, $p < .005$).

Based on these findings, it could be concluded that openness, extraversion and spousal communication are predictors of marital instability. The study proposes that marital relationship with good and effective communication improves stability in marriage.

Keywords: Openness, Extraversion, Spousal communication and Marital instability

Introduction:

Marriage is one of the most important relationships between a man and a woman. It involves emotional and legal commitment that is important in any adult life. Marriage is the oldest social institution ordained by God as well as the culture of many societies as a social contract between two individuals to become husband and wife and start a family. Dessislav (2019) observes that the family is the most basic unit of society and building block for national development. Just as there cannot be any society without families, there cannot be sustainable development without stable families and these can be fostered in an environment that is free of marital instability. In the past, marital instability among couples was rare as they were not as widespread as they are today. This is due to interference by various factors such as industrialization, technological development, expansion of cities and incursion of western lifestyles into the Nigerian society. Marriage and family life have undergone major changes during the past few decades globally Gardner, (2020) as the marriage institution is witnessing instability globally at an unprecedented rate Malone-Colon, (2021).

According to Alan Booth, marital instability is defined as the gamut of activities from thinking about and discussing divorce to actually filing for either separation or divorce. It is used to describe interpersonal difficulties within the marital relationship. Marital instability may however mean different things to different scholars but is usually used to refer to the process whereby marriages break down through separation, desertion or divorce Lee, (2020). The fragility of the marital bond is a notable feature of the contemporary world. Marital instability is always an undesirable human tragedy which causes hurt and suffering to couples. It is an experience, which involves serious disruption of life at many levels. Many people who have been through the experience of marital instability liken it to the experience of bereavement Asa & Nkan, (2018). Marriage instability has hindered the growth and progress of many homes and children in Nigeria Omoniyi-Onafunke, (2022). Marital instability is always a human tragedy that is desired by no one. It causes hurt and suffering to its victims. It is an experience which involves serious disruption of life at many levels. Marital instability has become a thing associated with the contemporary family institution. This however, is not to say that it had never once occurred in marital situation of the past but that the rate at which it occurs in contemporary society is quite alarming.

Garba (2020) observes that the rate of marital instability has increased particularly in urban areas where rich people entice people's wives with their money and couples are exposed to more outside experiences. This is common in our contemporary marital institution than before. Many other factors may be responsible for the high rate of marital instability in the country. For instance, Tolorunleke (2019) avers that communication, cultural background, family type, educational attainment, childbearing, religious affiliation, type of marriage, income and age of marriage are some of the major factors responsible for marital instability. This study will examine whether personality types and spousal communication play a role in marital instability among young couples in the study area.

Personality refers to a collection of emotional, thought and behavioural patterns that are unique to each individual and relatively stable over time. Personality has been conceptualized from a variety of theoretical perspectives and according to numerous sources. Sullivan (1953) highlighted the repetitive nature of behavioural patterns in addition to the contribution of Allport

(1961), who regarded the dynamic psycho-physiological systems as responsible for individuals' typical behaviour and thoughts. Eysenck (1975) regarded personality (viz. temperament and intellect) as being observable physical characteristics of body shapes. Informed by these different perspectives, personality, for the purpose of this research, is regarded as an intra-psychic construct consisting of an integrated and dynamic organization of an individual's psychological, social, moral and physical characteristics, determined by the reciprocal interaction with the social environment.

Psychologists define personality as a dynamic concept describing the growth and development of a person's whole psychological system. Other than looking at part of the person, personality looks at some aggregate whole that is greater than the sum of the parts (Robbins, 2020). Personality is a combination of thoughts, emotions and motivation of individuals. It is an interpersonal dynamic structure which includes physical and psychological systems and the component provides individuals' thoughts and behaviour characteristics Allport, (1961).

Allport (1937) had earlier defined personality as a dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determine his unique adjustments to his environment. It is made up of the characteristic thoughts, feelings, and behaviours that make a person distinctive or unique. This arises from within the individual and remains fairly consistent throughout life. Personality is also defined as the dynamic organization of those traits and characteristic patterns of behaviour that are unique to the individual Callahan, (1996). It has a long-lasting feature which is not easily affected by the external interferences. Wood (2018) referred to personality as the characteristics that distinguish persons based on their unique thoughts and actions.

One of the foremost researchers in the structure of personality was Raymond Cattell who conceptualized personality as being made up of sixteen distinct personality traits Cattell, (1955). All of these theories are based loosely on Gordon Allport's trait theory of personality which identified 171 personality traits Allport, (1937). Traits have been described as generalized personality dispositions that account for regularities in the functioning of a person across situations and over time Pervin, (2015). Although Cattell's 16-factor theory of personality (16PF) reduced Allport's 171 traits to a more manageable 16, it was later found that this structure could not be reliably replicated. Eysenck (1975) introduced a more parsimonious theory consisting of only three factors. Additional research determined that this structure did not sufficiently account for variances in personality, and the five-factor model was introduced. This study adopts the five-factor model of personality.

The five-factor model is a trait-based theory of personality which is based on five dimensions and is popularly known as the Big Five: Extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience Costa & McCrae, (2010). Each of these dimensions of personality encompasses a wide range of traits. Extraversion refers to a state where individuals show more concern towards what is happening outside. It is the opposite of introversion which refers to a state when an individual is concerned only with his/her own life and nothing else. Agreeableness is a personality trait which teaches the individual to be adjusted in almost all situations. Conscientiousness requires the individual to be sensitive to his/her

conscience. Conscientious people tend to be trustworthy, self-disciplined and achievement oriented. Neuroticism refers to one's tendency to experience negative thoughts and feelings such as anxiety, hostility, impulsivity, depression and low self-esteem. Openness to experience is a trait that makes individuals to seek new knowledge, skills and experiences. People who score high on openness are quite broadminded and modern in their outlook as compared to individuals who score low on the same parameter. Such individuals are conservative, reluctant to changes and have a traditional approach in life.

Thus, people with different personality traits can have different attitudes toward different aspects of life that influence marital quality and satisfaction. Personality traits may also have important role in determining the quality of marriage among newly-wed or young couples. For example, both (low) neuroticism and (high) conscientiousness in the five-factor model predict higher quality intimate relationships [Malouff, Thorsteinsson, Bhullar, & Rooke, \(2021\)](#). For the five-factor model traits that reflect social behaviour more directly, agreeableness has a consistent positive association with relationship quality, whereas extraversion has a weaker and less consistent positive association ([Malouff et al., 2021](#)), but some scholars found a negative association. There is disagreement on the role of personality types on marital quality.

Spousal communication, which simply refers to communication between couples, is an important means of interpersonal interactions among married people. Communication refers to a process of delivering and accepting messages. Effective spousal communication is therefore crucial for strong and healthy relationships which eventually give birth to marital stability. When communication between the couples begins to deteriorate, it means that the marriage is headed down the road to divorce. A marriage without effective communication is likely to crumble since communication is a livewire of marriage relationships or any other meaningful relationship [Esere, \(2018\)](#). Problems escalate when there is no communication, and many problems are resolved when there is effective communication. For sure, communication is the key to successful marriage, and without communication no marriage can survive in this divorce-filled world we live in [Jolin, \(2021\)](#). Most marriages are nowadays ending in divorce as a result of lack of communication. According to [Idowu and Esere \(2017\)](#), more than half of the failed relationships are due to the fact that there was a severe lack of communication between couples. In order to have a long and lasting relationship with someone, one must have excellent communication skills.

[Esere, Yusuf and Omotosho \(2019\)](#) observe that marriage without effective communication is likely to crumble because communication is fundamental to any relationship, especially marital relationships. Ineffective communication in marriage, which refers to the inability of the spouses to efficiently communicate with each other, can lead to numerous marital problems such as weak emotional bonding and excessive marital conflicts which causes marital instability [Esere & Idowu, \(2018\)](#); [Mamak, \(2020\)](#). Effective spousal communication is therefore crucial for strong and healthy relationships which eventually give birth to marital stability.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing rate of divorce and domestic violence among married couples resulting from marital instability is a source of concern to stakeholders in Nigeria which is witnessing a high rate of marital dissolution. These occurrences can harm the social, psychological, emotional, academic and economic lives of the persons affected as well as their children. Marriage is the major avenue whereby the society is populated. Thus, marital instability produces negative multiplier effects on the Nigerian society. The rate at which couples are experiencing marital instability and divorce is quite terrifying. This calls for a deep analysis of the new unacceptable way of life in order to understand their causative factors especially spousal communication and personality trait differences.

Marital instability has hindered the growth and progress of many homes and children and the society at large the effect of these cannot be over emphasized from drug addiction, armed robbery, commercial sex workers and many other criminal activity

When communication between couples becomes strained, their relationship may suffer if it is not checked in time. However, it appears that there is a dearth of empirical data on the possible predictive roles of personality types and spousal communication on marital instability among young couples in Nigeria. Besides, many studies have shown that personality types and spousal communication are important predictors of marital quality or state. However, little is known about their combined impact. Consequently, this study aims at investigating personality types and spousal communication as predictors of marital instability among young couples in Ogun State. The following hypotheses were formulated:

HO₁: There is no significance combined contribution of openness extraversion and spousal communication on marital instability among young couples in Ogun State.

HO₂: The second hypothesis states there is no significant contribution of openness and extraversion to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State.

Research Design

This study adopts the descriptive research design using the survey which will enable the researcher to collect data from a sample of the target population without manipulating either of the independent or predictor variables but measuring them as they pre-exist among the participants in this study. This is because the independent or predictor variables being investigated has already occurred and the researcher will only be interested in determining their influence on the dependent or criterion variables.

In this design, personality type and spousal communication are the independent variables, while marital instability is the dependent or criterion variable. The design will allow the researcher not only to determine the influence of each of the independent variables on the dependent variable, but also to study the joint or combined influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Results:

HO₁: There is no significance combined contribution of openness, extraversion and spousal communication on marital instability among young couples in Ogun State.

Table 1: Model summary and multiple regression coefficients for combined contribution of openness, extraversion and spousal communication on marital instability and spousal communication to marital instability.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	30.589	2.180		14.029	.000
Openness	.089	.060	.071	1.491	.137
Extraversion	- .068	.066	-.049	-1.024	.307
Spousal communication	-.581	.044	-.620	-13.214	.000
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig.
Regression	1094.531	3	364.84	61.184	.000
Residual	1633.98.2	274	5.963		
Total	2728.512	280			
R = .633, R ² = .401, Adj.R ² = .388, Std Error = 2.44201					

Dependent Variable: Marital Instability.

Predictors: (Constant), Spousal Communication, openness, extraversion.

This table revealed that with all the predictor variables entered into the model at the same time, there were significant results ($F_{(3,274)} = 61.184, p < .005$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that there is a significant combined contribution of personality type and spousal communication. This model is statistically significant as indicated by a large F value (61.184) and a p value of .000. This means that the independent variables in the model are collectively related to the dependent variable. The R-squared value of .401 indicates that 40.1% of the variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables in the model. The adjusted R squared value of .388 takes into account the number of independent variables in the model. The coefficient of determination (R) is .633, which means that there is a moderate positive correlation between the independent and dependent variable.

HO₂: The second hypothesis states there is no significant contribution of openness and extraversion to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State.

Table 2:Regression coefficients for contribution of Openness and Extraversion to marital instability.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	22.276	2.666		8.354	.000
Openness	.037	.076	.029	.484	.629
Extraversion	-.061	.084	-.044	-.729	.466
Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	53.352	2	10.666	1.096	.363
Residual	2675.181	272	9.728		
Total	2728.512.	280			
R = 140, R ² (Adj).002, Std.Error=3.11896					

Dependent variable: Marital instability

The table above revealed non-significant results. The null hypothesis is therefore upheld, leading to the conclusion that there is no significant contribution of personality types on marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State. Specifically, openness had no significant contribution to marital instability (Beta = .029, t = .484, p > .05). Extraversion (Beta = .044, t = -.729, p > .05) had no significant contribution to marital instability. The regression model did not show statistical significance in predicting the dependent variable. This indicates that these personality traits do not have a significant impact on the dependent variables

In conclusion, based on the results of this regression analysis, it does not appear that these personality traits, as measured by this model have a significant impact on the dependent variable. Further research may be needed to explore other potential factors that influence the dependent variable.

HO₂: There will be no significant contribution of spousal communication to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu Ogun State.

Table 2: Regression coefficients for contribution of spousal communication to marital instability.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig
(Constant)	26.273	.643		40.844	.000
Spousal Communication	-.570	.045	-.608	-12.796	.000
Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	1009.070	1	1009.70	163.134	.000
Residual	1719.442	279	9.728		
Total	2728.512	280	6.163		
R = .608, R ² = .370, R ² (Adj) = .368, Std Error = 2.48251					

Dependent variable: Marital instability

The table above revealed significant results (Beta = -.608, t = 12.796, p < .05). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. It is subsequently concluded that there is a significant contribution of spousal communication on marital instability among teachers in Sagamu Ogun State.

The regression model shows statistical significance in predicting the dependent variable. The coefficient for spousal communication is statistically significant at p < .001, indicating that it has a significant impact on the dependent variable in this model. The negative beta value for spousal communication (-.608) suggests that as spousal communication increases, the dependent variable decreases. The t value of -12.796 further supports the significance of this relationship.

The regression model explains a substantial amount of the variation in the dependent variable as shown by the high F value and the large sum of squares for regression, this indicates that the independent variable, spousal communication is a strong predictor of the dependent variable.

Discussion of Findings

This study aimed at examining personality types and spousal communication as predictors of marital instability. The findings of this research revealed that with all the predictor variables entered into the model at the same time, there were significant results. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that there is a significant combined contribution of openness, extraversion, spousal communication on marital stability. This also shows that there is a joint contribution of the independence variables was significant. This agrees with the submission of Engel et al (2022). The findings of the work conclude that there is no significant contribution of these personality types to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State. Specifically, openness had no significant contribution to marital instability had no significant contribution to marital instability. Openness dimension could likely be described as curious, open minded, and cultured, whereas an individual who has a low score on openness would likely be more narrow, unreflective, artistically insensitive, conservative, and conventional in his/her behaviour.

In conclusion, based on the results of this regression analysis, it does not appear that the personalities traits, as measured by this model, have a significant impact on the dependent variable. This is supported by the work of Dyrenforth et al. (2010) and Orths, (2013) specifically high levels of neuroticism were found to be negatively correlated with indicator of relationship dissatisfaction, conflict, abuse, and even relational termination. Further research may be needed to explore other potential factors that influence the dependent variable

The findings revealed significant result. It is subsequently concluded that there is a significant contribution of spousal communication on marital instability among teachers in Sagamu Ogun State. In conclusion, based on the results of this regression analysis, spousal communication has a significant impact on the dependent variable. This is supported by the work of (2008), communication is the key to a strong, healthy relationship. It allows partners to feel love and care.

Overall, the result suggest that personality traits such as openness and extraversion may have some impact on spousal communication but not necessarily on marital instability.

Conclusion

Based on the finding and discussion above, it could be concluded that personality types and spousal communication have significant relationship to marital instability. Hence, openness, extroversion and spousal communication combined together could be said to be predictors on marital instability.

Recommendation

Based on the summary and conclusion drawn from the major findings, the following recommendations are made;

There is need for self-awareness before going into marital relationship where individuals would be aware of their personality types.

There should be pre-marital counseling opportunities for pre-marital couples to be aware and equipped for the marital relationship.

The art of active listening should be encouraged and taught as a life skill to listen carefully, control the criticism, stick to the topic, give in sometimes and don't always be the focus.

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